

PROMOTION OF SALES IN THE FIELD OF PRODUCTION

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Abstract. *This article focuses on moving production and adapting it to market requirements. It also analyzes a particular enterprise by taking and examining the production system and examining the causes and consequences of its future income and whether its current year's income is low or high. If the income is high, this is a good conclusion, if the income is medium, the factor that causes it will be found and it will be improved. If the income is below the average, the factors that pull the enterprise back are sought and they are revised. The modification is reversible if possible, and this factor is removed if it is not possible to re-benefit from it, that is, it is not overpriced by its re-production.*

Keywords: *income, production, enterprise, money, funds, business, industry, reconstruction, re-production, quality, productivity, income.*

Introduction. Hanging production is an important part of every business, as it allows you to maximize production and use resources. The need to produce more in a short time has led many companies to apply the production shift system. This article affects the business efficiency of the production shift.

In recent years, the manufacturing industry has undergone rapid changes, new technologies and techniques have been mastered. One of the trends that hit the industry with a storm is the production replacement system. This system consists of dividing the production process into shifts, with each team running for a certain period of time before being replaced by another. This article will look at the work replacement systems that develop and how they are changing the manufacturing industry. Methods:

Methods of economic analysis are divided into 2 groups:

1. Simple methods;

2. Mathematical methods

1. Simple methods

compare,

grouping,

calculation of absolute and relative indicators,

balance and chain link.

Correlation-regrational analysis method

Method of logorifms

Determinant method

Matrix method

Linear programming method

Theoretical game method

2. On the application of the mathematical method

- the period of execution of economic analysis is accelerated;

- it will be possible to accurately calculate the effect of changes and connections;

- complex factors that cannot be calculated by simple, traditional methods and the possibility of a full study of the multifactorial;
- the calculation will be easier to use technically, etc.

3. A comparison is a comparison with the aim of identifying similarities or differences between related objects. With them, a comparison of general and private economic phenomena is carried out, changes in the level of studied objects, trends and their development.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. The data analyzed showed a significant increase in production and productivity in enterprises using a production shift system. The ceiling system provided a continuous flow of production, since there was always one group on duty. This helped reduce downtime and thus increased production. Quality has also improved, as more time has been devoted to checking finished products for errors and defects. Employees who worked in the shift system became more alert, errors decreased, and the quality of work improved. In general, enterprises that used the production shift system were more efficient. The data showed a significant increase in productivity and efficiency for companies using Shift Production Systems. The system helped to eliminate interruptions, since there was always a team to work with the equipment. In addition, employees who worked on the shift system were more alert.

The adoption of the production shift system has had a positive impact on business efficiency in terms of production, quality and productivity. Production switching systems provided a continuous flow of production, which helped businesses achieve their goals faster. This also allowed better use of resources, as there was always a team to work with the equipment, reducing downtime. The system also helped improve the quality of work by allowing better attention to error and defect testing.

"UZBAT A.O. "If we look at the joint venture of JSC, we will conduct an analysis of the rain in it. Let's look at the data of the enterprise in 2017 and 2018.

№	Specification	2017-year	2018-year
1	Revenue from product sales	129 165 804	234 876 123
2	Costs	65 789 098	87 987 567
3	Net profit	63 376 706	146 888 556

As can be seen from the indicators, the enterprise was profitable in both years. If we compare the net profit in the base year and the net profit in the current year, $146\ 888\ 556 - 63\ 376\ 706 = 83\ 511\ 850$. If we analyze the enterprise factors one by one, the income from the sale of products in the current year is 234 876 more than the income earned in the base year. $123 - 129\ 165\ 804 = -105\ 710\ 319$ more fell. This is as follows in a relative measure: $234\ 876\ 123 : 129\ 165\ 804 = 1.8184$. As for the cost, there is a lot of cost compared to the base year. This is definitely a surplus for the company. But the production institution may have used this money for re-production or investment. Despite this, the company made a profit with a high (+) profit. That is, net profit: $146\ 888\ 556 - 63\ 376\ 706 = 83\ 511\ 850$. If we want to calculate it in coefficients, more precisely, if we want to get a relative measure, we will get $146\ 888\ 556 : 63\ 376\ 706 = 2.317705$. It can be seen that JSC "UZBAT A.O." has a profit for the current year.

The adoption of production shift systems is becoming increasingly popular among enterprises. The data analyzed in this study showed that the system has a positive effect on business performance, resulting in increased output, improved quality, and improved efficiency. Businesses

are encouraged to learn how to apply manufacturing change systems to help them improve efficiency and maximize resources.

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